

Effect Of Bibliotherapy on Low Self-Esteem Among Junior Secondary School Students in Anambra State

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Abstract

This study seeks to determine effect of bibliotherapy on low self-esteem among public junior secondary school students junior Secondary School Students (JSS) in Anambra State. Three research questions were posed and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The design for this study is true experimental design. The population of students with low self-esteem is 310. A sample of 50 students with low self-esteem was selected for the study and purposive sampling techniques was used in choosing two schools in the study area. Index of self-Esteem by Hudson (1982) was used for data collection. Paired samples t-test was used to analyzed the first and second hypothesis and independent t-test was used to analyzed the third hypothesis. Result showed that the first hypothesis which stated that there is no significance difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores of male students with low self-esteem exposed to bibliotherapy was rejected at $t(12) = 9.24, P < .05$. Result also showed that the second hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores of female students with low self- esteem exposed to bibiotherapy was rejected at $t(12) = 17.66, p < .05$. Finally, result revealed that the third hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between post-test mean scores of male and female students with low self - esteem exposed to bibiotherapy was accepted at $t(48) = 2.163, P > .05$. Therefore, based on these findings, it was recommended that school guidance counsellors should adopt bibliotherapy in helping students with low self - esteem to improve in their self- esteem, Professional counsellors should organize periodic bibliotherapy sessions with the aim of boosting the self-esteem of their students in order to improve on their academic performance of students other areas of their life and among others

Keywords: *Effect, Bibliotherapy, Self-Esteem, Secondary School, Students*

Introduction

Self-esteem is regarded as an important variable for personal happiness and effective functioning of individuals. Individuals need self-esteem to overcome their problems effectively, feel better, and reach personal goals. According to Hamm in Nurten (2012), self-esteem is an

attitude of approval or disapproval and indicates the extent to which the individual believes himself to be capable, significant, successful and worthy. It is a person's negative or positive feelings and interpretations of successes and failures in life. A person's self-esteem can be high or low.

High self-esteem means having feelings of confidence, worthiness and positive regard for oneself. Individuals with high self-esteem feel respectable, worthy, but not superior. It could also be seen in the evaluation of self; having high self-esteem means that an individual likes himself or herself. Nwokolo and Oguzie (2021) observed that people with high self-esteem feel a sense of belonging and security, respect themselves and appreciate others. They also tend to be successful in life because they feel confident in taking on challenges and risking failure to achieve desired purposes.

On the contrary, individuals with low self-esteem do not satisfy themselves, and reject their selves. Having low self-esteem could suggest that an individual feels uncomfortable about himself. Kim and Lee stated that low self-esteem leads to helplessness, fear, depression, insecurity, anxiety, acting-out behaviour, and sleep problems. The authors further pointed out that low self-esteem makes people to avoid seeking new jobs, initiating relationships, or learning new skills for fear of rejection or failure. Many avoid social setting and refrain from sharing their opinions for the same reasons.

According to Harter (1999), two factors play an important role in the development and maintenance of self-esteem in children and adolescents: (1) perceived competence in areas of importance, and (2) the experience of social support. Domains of perceived competence not only have a direct impact on self-esteem, but also influence approval and support of parents and peers. That is, good academic competence and behavioural conduct elicit approval and support of parents, whereas good physical appearance, relationships to peers, and athletic competence result in approval and support of peers (Harter, 2003).

Many children and adolescents maintain a positive view of themselves by achieving success in domains of perceived competence (Crocker & Park, 2003). For example, boys who are relatively good in football may play football more frequently and may invest more time in training. As a consequence, their football skills increase even further and their self-esteem remains high. However, adolescents appear to not always be capable of achieving success, which makes them to engage in strategies to protect, maintain or enhance their self-esteem levels. In the face of failure, children and adolescents may use strategies such as downward social comparison (comparing themselves with others that are worse off), external attributions (attributing failure to external causes), or reduce the importance of the domain on which they fail to achieve success (Crocker & Park, 2003).

Possible factors likely to negatively affect the self-esteem of secondary school students could include experiences of enuresis (i.e. bedwetting) and aggressive behaviours. Enuresis involves the inappropriate deposit of waste in terms of location, timing, or frequency (Williams, Jackson & Friman, 2007). American Psychiatric Association (APA) Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders – Fifth Edition (DSM-V) defines enuresis as the repeated voiding of urine into the bed or clothes which causes significant distress or impairment in important areas of functioning (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). In the present study, nocturnal enuresis (NE), which refers to voiding urine during the night and in the bed only, is suspected to be one of the factors predisposing to low self-esteem among junior secondary school students.

Again, inflicting harm on other students is an aggressive behaviour suspected to be capable of leading to low self-esteem on the victims. According to Bordens and Horowitz (2008), social psychologists define aggression as any behaviour that is intended to inflict harm (whether psychological or physical) on another organism or object. The key factor to note in this definition is the intention to harm, without which, such behaviour may not be classified as aggression. As such, the harm need not be physical only, it also include psychological harm. Instances of behaviours among these students which can be supposed to be aggressive include bullying of other students, beating, hitting, and laying abuses on other students because one is a senior or stronger than them, among others. Consequently, Obikeze and Obi (2015) noted that one of the recent issues concerning both the media and parents is the aggressive behaviour of secondary school students, and such could negatively affect the self-esteem level of the victimized students. In a study by Obinwa (2017), it was reported, among others, that secondary school students with low self-esteem differed significantly from secondary school students with high self-esteem on aggression among community secondary school students.

According to Okafor, Obi and Oguzie (2018), male adolescence shows more high self-esteem than the females. One possible explanation for this is difference is gender roles; many qualities associated with the male role are consistent with high self-esteem. Okafor, Obi and Oguzie opined that self-esteem is a stereo typically masculine trait; boys develop high self-esteem, whereas the presentation of high self-esteem in girls is sometimes considered a breach of traditional gender roles. However, Radhwan (2015) revealed that both male and female students can have and manifest high self-esteem.

As noted by Nwokolo and Oguzie (2021), most male and female children begin their primary schools with high self-esteem. They learn to read with the attitude that they are simply the best and are encouraged by all who surround them; their teachers, families and peers. Wadsworth, however, observed that this changes as time goes by as 80% of the children who were classified

with high self-esteem drop to a staggering 20% low self-esteem on entering secondary schools. In most cases, these children with low self-esteem feel that the important adults and peers in their lives do not accept them, do not care about them very much, and would not go out of their way to ensure their safety and well-being.

Self-esteem is a central concept that is related to academic achievement, social functioning and psychopathology of adolescents. With respect to academic achievement, various studies indicate that adolescents with low self-esteem are less successful at school (Mann, Hosman, Schaalma & De Vries, 2004). With regard to social functioning, research demonstrated that children with low self-esteem are usually less accepted by their peers (Donders & Verschueren, 2004). Studies have equally shown that low self-esteem is related to child psychopathology, including anxiety (Muris, Meesters & Fijen, 2003), depression (Mann et al., 2004) and eating pathology (Muris, Meesters, Van de Blom & Mayer, 2005). Some scholars have found a strong relation between low self-esteem and externalising problems (Donnellan, Trzesniewski, Robins, Moffitt & Caspi, 2005).

Low self-esteem poses a great challenge to many youths and adults in the Nigerian society. For instance, Chinawa, Obu, Manyike, Obi, Israel and Chinawa (2014) reported that there are about two suicide attempts every month traceable to depression from low self esteem. The issue of low self-esteem among Nigerian students is of vital importance to teachers, parents and other educational stakeholders because of its negative impacts on their educational progress. Some Nigerian students exhibit low self-esteem through withdrawn and unresponsive behaviour, inability to make and keep friends, making cutting remarks against themselves and others and inability to work independently and complete common tasks. Low self-esteem also affects students' friendships, school achievement, life satisfaction and communication skills. In this regard, Paul, Alikor and Anochie (2013) posited that children with low self-esteem perform poorly in school compared with those with high self-esteem. These disturbing behaviours make it imperative to apply positive approaches towards helping students with manifestation of low self-esteem to overcome their behavioural problems. One of these approaches is the use of bibliotherapy books that emphasize self-esteem.

Bibliotherapy is a strategy of helping students deal with issues in their lives using books (Briggs & Pehrsson, 2008). It is the use of literature that addresses problems or issues current in the lives of children. Briggs and Pehrsson stated that bibliotherapy can help students become aware of many issues such as self-esteem, interactions with others, problem solving and emotional issues by clarifying feelings and validating emotions. McCulliss (2012) explained that bibliotherapy is

an expressive therapy that involves the reading of specific texts with the purpose of healing using an individual's relationship to the content of books and poetry and other written words as therapy.

Kang (2017) pointed out that bibliotherapy with picture books help children in several ways such as (i) to alleviate unhealthy feeling and attitude such as anxiety, depression, isolations, and sense of loss;(ii) to gain insight into their own life situation with problem-solving;(iii) to increase self-esteem; and(iv) to develop empathy with others. Bibliography has two forms; namely, developmental and clinical. Developmental bibliotherapy is used to anticipate issues before they become a problem. Developmental bibliotherapy is useful with children who are progressing through the normal stages of growth and who may benefit from an exploration into issues relevant to their age or experiences, such as low self-esteem. Clinical bibliotherapy, on the other hand is employed by trained guidance counsellors, psychologists and psychiatrists for use with children in therapy situations.

The main goals of bibliotherapy include providing information about problems, stimulating discussion about problems, communicating new values and attitudes and providing solutions to problems, but as a technique, bibliotherapy, has proven effective in both classroom and child therapy. It has been proven to be effective in the treatment of low self-esteem, depression, anger and other maladjustment behaviours in children in developed countries such as USA, UK with long lasting. Through reading, or being read a story similar to their own lives, children are able to experience and deal with issues more objectively which can then be applied to their own situation. In most cases, stories show the child that there is a way out, that others have the same issues, and that he or she is not isolated. This sends a message to the child that it is acceptable to discuss the problem together and work out a solution. Discussions provide a forum for the child to better understand what is being said in the story and apply it to his/her situation (McKenna, Hevey & Martin, 2010).

Furthermore, teachers, guidance counsellors, psychologists, parents and anyone coming in contact with a child who is experiencing low self-esteem can use this technique. Stamps (2009) observed that guidance counsellors in developed countries have used this technique quite successfully since the 1950s and 1960s. Stamps further explained that the process of bibliotherapy involves identification, catharsis and insight. Identification offers a possibility to identify with the character. The catharsis enables a release of emotions through the character's journey in the story while insight is a connection of the reader's experiences with those of the characters in the book.

Bibliotherapy uses literature to bring about a therapeutic interaction between the client and the therapist. Shechtman and Nir-Shfir (2008) stated that the idea of using literature is to help the child understand his situation better by reading a related material. With the use of bibliotherapy,

children may become aware of their underlying unconscious issues. Shechtman and Nir-Shfir further pointed out that bibliotherapy has for ages been considered as a powerful tool which can be used to guide children to enhance their self-esteem.

Bibliotherapy process could be a useful technique because it could allow the child to step back from his/her problem and experience it from an objective viewpoint. It could offer the child a safe avenue to investigate personal feelings. It could provide a non-threatening way for guidance counsellor to broach the sensitive malady affecting a child's development. Wendy (2011) asserted that parents, teachers and guidance counsellors in Nigeria, in their bid to handle issues of low self-esteem among secondary school students, should use bibliotherapy techniques which have proved successful in developed countries in increasing self-esteem among high school students. It is with this background that the researcher seeks to ascertain the effect of bibliotherapy on low self-esteem among junior secondary school students in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Low self-esteem among children has been recognized as a common behavioural problem both within and outside Nigeria. It often leads to helplessness, fear, depression, insecurity, anxiety, acting-out behaviour and sleep problems. Low self-esteem also affects students' friendships, life satisfaction, communication skills, and, more significantly, academic achievement (Paul et al., 2013).

To help children overcome the problem of low self-esteem, parents and guardians often use traditional techniques such as open communication, show of love and affection and reward system, among others. However, these techniques appear overly ineffective in taming this problem as a result of increase in the number of children with low self-esteem being recorded on daily basis. There is therefore need to apply modern techniques such as assertiveness training, cognitive restructuring and bibliotherapy which shown to be effective in managing the problem of low self-esteem among children in developed countries. Therefore the problem of this study is that the number of secondary school students in Anambra State with low self-esteem continues to rise. This means that these traditional techniques have not proved effective and makes this study on the effect of bibliotherapy on low self-esteem among junior secondary school students in Anambra State imperative.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. What is the effect of bibliotherapy on low self-esteem among male junior secondary school students in Anambra State when their pretest and posttest mean scores are compared?

2. What is the effect of bibliotherapy on low self-esteem among female junior secondary school students in Anambra State when their pretest and posttest mean scores are compared?
3. What are the differences in the effect of bibliotherapy on male and female junior secondary school students with low self-esteem using their post-test mean scores?

Method

This study adopted pretest-post-test design. Frankfort-Nachmias and Nachmias (1996) defined this design as an experimental design for a study where one group is tested twice for mean comparison. Hence, the current study used this design on the bases that the same participants were tested twice (before treatment and after treatment). The population of this study comprised of all 310 junior secondary school class II (JSS2) students in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State. The sample for this study was 50 (24 male students and 26 female students) from two secondary schools in Awka selected using purposive sampling. The instrument used for data collection for the study was Index of Self-Esteem (ISE) developed by Hudson in 1982. It is a 25-item instrument designed to measure self-esteem. It is scored using Likert response pattern of 1 to 5, where 1 = Rarely or none of the time, 2 = A little of the time, 3 = Some of the time, 4 = A good part of the time, and 5 = Most of the time. Mean and t-test were used for data analysis.

Results

Table 1: Pretest and post-test mean scores of male students with low self-esteem exposed to bibliotherapy

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Post-Test Mean	Gained Mean	Remark
Paired Sample	24	55.75	25.87	29.88	Much Difference

Table 1 indicates that the male students had pretest mean score of 55.33 and post-test mean score of 25.88 with gained mean score of 29.88 in their low self-esteem. This means that bibliotherapy is effective on male junior secondary school students' low self-esteem.

Table 2: Pretest and post-test mean scores of female students with low self-esteem exposed to bibliotherapy

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Post-Test Mean	Gained Mean	Remark
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Paired Sample	26	57.08	25.51	29.56	Much Difference
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Table 2 indicates that the female students had pretest mean score of 57.08 and post-test mean score of 27.51 with gained mean score of 29.56 in their low self-esteem. This means that bibliotherapy is effective on female junior secondary school students' low self-esteem.

Table 3: Post-test mean scores of female and male students with low self-esteem exposed to bibliotherapy

Source of Variation	N	Female Post-test Mean	Male Post-Test Mean	Gained Mean Difference	Remark
Independent Groups Compared	50	27.51	25.87	1.64	Slight Difference

Table 3 indicates that the female student participants had post-test mean score of 27.51 and that male student participants had post-test mean score of 25.87 with gained mean difference score of 1.64 in their low self-esteem. This means that bibliotherapy has little difference in its effect on low self-esteem between male and female junior secondary school students.

Table 4: Summary Table of Paired-Samples T-Test on Effect of Bibliotherapy on Low Self-Esteem among Male Participants

Source	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	T	Df	Sig
ISE of Male Participants Before (1 st Week)- After (6 th Week) Bibliotherapy Application on Low Self-Esteem	18.53846	7.22975	24	9.24	12	.000
<i>P<.05</i>						

Table 4 above shows that the observed difference in the mean scores between pretest and post-test of bibliotherapy application on low self-esteem reached significant level at $t(12) = 9.24, p < .05$. This means that significant difference exists in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of male junior secondary school students treated with bibliotherapy for low self-esteem. Therefore, the hypothesis was rejected.

Table 5: Summary Table of Paired-Samples T-Test on Effect of Bibliotherapy on Low Self-Esteem among Female Participants

Source	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	T	Df	Sig
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ISE of Female Participants Before (1st Week)-

16.00000	3.26599	26	17.66	12	.000
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After (6th Week)
Bibliotherapy Application
on Low Self-Esteem

P<.05

Table 5 above shows that the observed difference in the mean scores between pretest and post-test of bibliotherapy application on low self-esteem reached significant level at $t(12) = 17.66, p<.05$. This means that significant difference exists in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of female junior secondary school students treated with bibliotherapy for low self-esteem. Therefore, the hypothesis was rejected.

Table 6: Summary Table of T-test on Gender Difference on Effect of Bibliotherapy on Low Self-Esteem

Source	Gender	N	T	Df	Sig
Bibliotherapy on Low Self-Esteem	Male	24	2.163	48	.13
	Female	26			

P<.05

Table 6 above shows that the observed difference in the mean of the two groups failed to reach significant level at $t(48) = 2.163, P>.05$. Therefore, the third null hypothesis was accepted. So, the slight mean difference on the effect of bibliotherapy on low self-esteem between female and male students was not significant.

Discussion

The result of the study showed that the comparison made on pretest and post-test of bibliotherapy application in treating low self-esteem among male junior secondary school students revealed that the treatment was effective in improving their self-esteem. The finding showed that the mean gain score from pretest and post-test of male students attained much difference status, thereby reaching a significant difference between the two assessment periods as was shown in table 4.

This finding agrees with the result reported in a study carried out by Karacan and Guneri (2010) on the effect of self-esteem enrichment bibliocounseling program on the self-esteem of

sixth grade students in Ankara. These scholars adopted an experimental design consisting of one treatment group and one treatment control group and two measurements (pre and post). They randomly selected twenty-four (13 female, 11 male) participants. Data analysis via Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) revealed a result indicating a significant increase in the self-esteem scores of treatment-group subjects, as measured by the Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory (CSEI).

The finding of the current study indicated that the comparison made on pretest and post-test of bibliotherapy application in treating low self-esteem among female junior secondary school students showed an improved self-esteem. This finding revealed that the mean gain score from pretest and post-test of female students attained much difference status, thereby reaching a significant difference between the two assessment periods, as was shown in table 5.

Accordingly, this finding obtained in the current study is in agreement with the finding reported by Salimi, Zare-Farashbandi, Papi, Samouei and Hassanzadeh (2014). These scholars carried out a study examining the effect of group bibliotherapy on the self-esteem of female students of Isfahan University of Medical Sciences living in dormitory. The study was designed to be an interventional semi-experimental study with pre-test and post-test and control group. The groups were assessed in post test after 1 month. Descriptive statistics (means and frequencies distribution) and inferential statistics (independent *t*- test, paired *t*- test and mannwhitney) were used to analyze the data collected. The result then revealed that group bibliotherapy had positive and significant effect on general, family, professional and total self esteem of female students living in dormitories.

The result showed that the difference between post –test scores of female and male junior secondary school students with low self-esteem exposed to bibliotherapy was slight. This slight difference indicated that the effect of bibliotherapy on each gender appeared to be relatively the same, resulting to no slight gain mean score and no significant difference, as was shown in table 6.

However, this result obtained disagrees with the findings reported by Karacan and Guneri (2010) that carried out a study on the effect of self-esteem enrichment bibliocounseling program on the self-esteem of sixth grade students in Ankara. Being an experimental study, it used one treatment group and one no-treatment control group and two measurements (pre and post). 13 females and 11 males, who were randomly selected and assigned to a treatment group or a control group, constituted participated. Findings indicated a significant increase in the self-esteem scores of treatment-group subjects, as measured by the Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory (CSEI).

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it was concluded that application of bibliotherapy will significantly reduce low self-esteem among junior secondary school students irrespective of gender. If well undertaken, it will expose junior secondary school students with low self-esteem to ways of improving their self-esteem.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the main study, the following recommendations were made:

1. School guidance counselors should adopt bibliotherapy in helping low self-esteem students to improve their self-esteem.
2. Professional counselors should organize periodic bibliotherapy sessions with the aim of boosting the self-esteem of their students in order to improve on their academic performance of students other areas of their life.
3. Curriculum developers should integrate bibliotherapy as a technique in the curriculum for guidance counsellors.

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